

111064

111061

V 109.0517 E500/N2900 →
109.94 06 To E500/N3010
 ↙ ERROR

PMS01 LOCATE SURVEY POINTS
A₉, B₉, C₉, D₉, E₉

A₉ - Out of view

B₉ - H 383.4172
 8589
V 113.9044

SP 41.188 }
 41.195 }
 41.190 }
 41.190 }

40.217

H 50.5808

V 100.8055

SD 65.791

65.798

65.798

P 65.692

E500/N2900 →
E500/N3010

109.0734

110.048

1110.612

1110.685 1110.695

P 109.938

.062 cm